

The level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs

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Abstract

This study explores the level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs, highlighting key factors that influence their engagement with digital tools and platforms. By examining barriers, motivations, and strategies, the research aims to identify trends and best practices that empower women in the digital marketplace. The findings reveal varying degrees of adoption based on industry, access to resources, and educational background, ultimately suggesting that targeted support and training could enhance digital marketing capabilities for women entrepreneurs.

Key words: Digital marketing adoption, Women entrepreneurs, Engagement, Digital tool Platforms, Barriers, Training, Capabilities

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving business landscape, digital marketing has emerged as a crucial component for success, especially for entrepreneurs. Among these entrepreneurs, women are increasingly leveraging digital platforms to expand their reach, enhance brand visibility, and drive sales. However, the level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs varies significantly across different sectors and regions. This disparity can be attributed to a variety of factors, including access to resources, technological literacy, and societal expectations.

Understanding the extent to which women entrepreneurs engage with digital marketing is vital for identifying both opportunities and challenges within this demographic. By examining the barriers they face, their motivations for adopting digital strategies, and the successful practices they employ, we can gain valuable insights into how to better support and empower women in the digital marketplace. This introduction sets the stage for a deeper exploration of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs, aiming to contribute to the ongoing discourse on gender equality and economic empowerment in the digital age.

Review of literature

Reema Bhagat (2021)¹ in their article titled “Digital Marketing Strategies Adopted by Women Entrepreneurs and its Impact on Business Performance” “The study analyzed the pattern of digital marketing media adoption among women entrepreneurs, identifying both the enablers and barriers to implementing digital marketing strategies. The researcher collected both primary and secondary data, with primary data gathered through a questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential data analyses were conducted to draw valid conclusions and achieve the study's objectives. Data analysis involved the use of chi-square tests and correlation tests. The findings revealed that 75% of respondents were utilizing some form of digital marketing for their business marketing and communication, indicating awareness of its importance. Notably, 80% of the women entrepreneurs operated in the small or micro business segment, aligning with recent reports from the MSME sector. The survey results showed a strong positive association between the level of digital marketing adoption and increased sales. The author suggested taking necessary steps to enhance digital marketing usage, encouraging women entrepreneurs to invest in learning digital skills to effectively utilize digital marketing tools in response to market needs. In conclusion, the study examined digital marketing adoption strategies and their impact on business performance among women entrepreneurs, particularly in the context of micro and small enterprises in Karnataka. The outcomes contribute to bridging research gaps and enhancing knowledge in this field.

Objective of the study

The primary objectives of this study on the level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs are as follows:

1. To evaluate the current level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs across various industries and regions.
2. To identify key factors that influence the engagement of women entrepreneurs with digital marketing tools, including technological access, education, and support networks.
3. To examine the barriers that hinder women entrepreneurs from fully utilizing digital marketing strategies, such as financial constraints, lack of technical skills, and societal expectations.
4. To explore the motivations behind women entrepreneurs' decisions to adopt digital marketing, including the desire for growth, competitiveness, and customer engagement.
5. To identify and highlight successful digital marketing strategies and practices employed by women entrepreneurs, providing actionable insights for others in the field.
6. To propose targeted recommendations for policymakers, educators, and support organizations aimed at enhancing digital marketing capabilities among women entrepreneurs.

By achieving these objectives, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the landscape of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs and to contribute to their empowerment in the digital economy.

Research Methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data.

Primary data

Primary data refers to original data collected specifically for this study. A structured questionnaire was used to gather information from women entrepreneurs.

Secondary data

Data will be collected from various publications, journals, articles related to the subject of study, websites, magazines, and other relevant materials.

Sampling Design and Data Analysis

The study aims to analyze the role of digital marketing in motivating entrepreneurship skill development programs, particularly among women entrepreneurs. Both primary and secondary data were collected. A convenience sampling method was used to select 100 respondents from the pool of women entrepreneurs.

Data analysis and interpretation

- i) Percentage Analysis
- ii) Graded Rank Test

A simple percentage analysis technique was used to identify the reasons women entrepreneurs choose entrepreneurship as a future career option. For this, the researcher identified five reasons that motivate women to start their enterprises.

Age composition of the respondents

Age are the most relevant factors when considering the socio- economic characteristics of the population. Age is an important factors showing the capability of the respondents to take up the risk and starting own business.

Table 1:Age of the respondents

S.No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Upto 25 years	25	25
2	25-35 years	40	40
3	35 -50 years	35	35
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

From the above table, it is clear that majority of 40% of the respondents are come under the age group between 25-35 years, 35% of the are age group 35-50 years and 25% of the respondents are comes under the age group are up to 25 years.

Table 2: Educational Qualification of women entrepreneurs

S.No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Up to School	10	10
2	Degree / Diploma Graduate	39	39
3	Post Graduate Degree	30	30
4	Professional Courses	21	21
	Total	100	100

From the above table, it is clear that majority of 39% of the respondent are come under below degree / diploma graduate education, 30 % of the respondent are come under post graduate degree, 21% of the respondent are come under professional courses, 10% of the respondent are come under up to school .

Table3 Hence you adopted digital marketing for your promoter

S.No	Types of digital marketing in adoption of digital marketing	Percentage	Rank
1	Social media marketing	20	I
2	Content marketing	15	III
3	Email marketing	14	IV
4	Pay per click	12	V
5	Affiliate marketing	6	VIII
6	Mobile marketing	18	II
7	Influencer marketing	5	VII
8	Search engine optimization	10	VI
9	Others	0	IX

Source: Primary data

Table 3 indicates 20 % result for social media marketing hold I Rank. Mobile marketing held II rank. Content marketing held III rank.

Finding

1. 40% of the respondents are come under the age group between 25-35 years,
2. 39% of the respondent are come under below degree / diploma graduate education.
3. 20 % result for social media marketing hold I Rank.

Suggestion

Develop targeted training programs focused on digital marketing skills tailored specifically for women entrepreneurs. These programs should cover essential topics such as social media marketing, search engine optimization, and content creation. Enhance access to digital tools and resources by providing grants or subsidies to women entrepreneurs. Collaborating with tech companies to offer discounted services could also help bridge the gap. Advocate for policies that support women entrepreneurs in the digital space, including initiatives that promote gender equality in access to technology and funding. By implementing these suggestions, stakeholders can help enhance the level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs, ultimately empowering them in the digital marketplace.

Conclusion

The level of digital marketing adoption among women entrepreneurs is a crucial factor in their business success and overall economic empowerment. This study highlights the varying degrees of engagement with digital marketing tools, influenced by factors such as access to resources, training, and support networks. While many women entrepreneurs recognize the potential of digital marketing to enhance their business visibility and growth, significant barriers still exist. By addressing these challenges and leveraging the opportunities within the digital landscape, women entrepreneurs can enhance their competitive edge and contribute to a more equitable economy. The continued exploration of this subject will be vital in developing effective strategies that further support women in their entrepreneurial journeys.